

SCHOOL FACILITIES AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN BIOLOGY IN CALABAR SOUTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, CROSS RIVER STATE

Osomasi, Richard Aja

Department of Curriculum and Instructional Technology, Faculty of Education, University of Cross River State (UNICROSS), Calabar, Nigeria.

Corresponding Author: richardosomasi518@gmail.com

Abstract

The purpose of this research was to investigate school facilities and students' academic achievement in Biology in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State. Two variables were identified for the study. These were used to formulate the research questions and hypotheses. The research design was a survey design. The population of the study was 700 in secondary schools in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State. The sample size comprised one hundred respondents (100). The research instrument was a questionnaire, titled School Facilities and Academic Achievement of students in biology (SFAASB), and the Biology Achievement Test (BAT), was used for the collection of data for the study. Independent t-test analysis was used to analyse the data. The findings revealed that the school library, the school laboratory and school instructional materials influence students' academic achievement of biology students in secondary school in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State. It was recommended that certain measures could be used by teaching staff and other top personnel in fostering quality assurance among teachers in the school. Also, the government should ensure that qualified teaching staff is available in order to promote their teaching effectiveness.

Keywords: School Facilities; Academic Achievement; Secondary School Students; Biology Education; Calabar South; Cross River State

Introduction

Background to the study

The aims and objectives of the school is to provide effective teaching, learning and acquisition of skills and knowledge that will be relevant to the needs of the society. This is made possible through proper use or relevant and functional faculties. So, everything's personnel and materials, in and around the social environment should be positively geared towards providing qualitative academic and practical skill which will facilitate achievement. This leads to focus the school and its position in terms of proper utilization of facilities in guaranteeing positive and good academic achievement of biology students. When the aims and objective of this positive academic achievement of the potent factors that contribute to academic achievement of students in biology in the school system. These facilities are those things that enable the teachers to carry out his/her work effectively, thus facilitate teaching and enhance effective and efficient learning outcome.

The school is simply a special place where basic learning facilities such as school laboratory, classroom facilities, study libraries and safety facilities are provided for learners to improve their academic achievement. Societies in the vein, worked for a proper enhancing of school, with staff and equipment (Cash, 2014).

A laboratory has been conceptualized as a room or building specially built for teaching by demonstration of theoretical phenomenon into practical term (Oguniyi, 2014). It is can also be described as a place where theoretical work is practicalized. Whereas practical in any learning experience involves students in activities such as observing, counting, measuring, experimenting, recording and carrying out field work. Farombi (2014), argued the saying that "seeing is believing" as the effect of using laboratories in teaching and learning of science and other science relating disciplines as a student tend

to understand and recall what they see than they hear or were told. Laboratory is essential to the teaching of science and the success of any science course is much dependent on the laboratory provision made for it, 2022 world book encyclopaedia defines a library as a collection of information, sources, resources and services, organized for use and maintained by a public body, an institution, or a private individual.

Library is an essential factor in teaching-learning process. It forms one of the most important educational services. The educational process functions in the students at his easy convenience, all books, periodical and other reproduced materials which as of interest and values to him as basic or supplementary textbooks. The school library is a library within school where students, staff, and often, parents of a public or private school have access to a variety of resources. The goal of school library is to ensure that all members of the school community have equitable access to books and reading, to information and to information technology.

The school library exists to provide a range of learning opportunities for both large and small groups as well as individual with a focus on intellectual content, information literacy and the learner. School library remains the power house of educational institution without a library is as lifeless as a motor car without an engine and a body without a soul (Daniel, 2014).it is one of those important facilities in a school, school facilities are vital tools in the teaching and learning process, hence the justification for their adequate provision and management (Krashen, 2015). The school facilities are divided into instructional, recreational, residential and general-purpose types. School facilities also include school building, e.g. Classroom, assembly halls, laboratories, workshops, libraries etc. They also include teaching aids, like the chalkboard, chairs, tables, devices such as modern educational hardware and software in the form of magnetic tapes, films and transparent stripes. School facilities are all the things that are needed for effective teaching-learning process to take place. They are designed to enhance the process of teaching. The absence of school facilities implies the non-existence of any set up that may be referred to as school.

Academic achievement is the extent to which a student or teacher of institution has attained their short or long-term educational goals.it is also a good measure of how well as student performs in an academic environment. Academic achievement is not limited to academic success, alone, but also include measure of how well a student handle the process of learning. Cash (2014) examine he relationship between school facilities and students' academic achievement in small rural Virginia high school. He found out that student score on achievement test, adjusted for social-economic status, was found to be up to 5 percentile points lower in building with lower quality ratings. He went further to say that academic achievement may be measured through students' grade point average whereas for institutions, achievement may be measured through graduation rates.

Castaidi in Peretemode (2014) concludes that educational facilities are those things of education which enables skilful teacher to teach what is possible when they are not provided. They depend mostly on the quality of available school facilities that are to be provided for such programme. This is supported by the view of Aderalegbe in Abraham (2015) who posits that the type of atmosphere required for effective learning is that which consist of better school buildings, more and better teaching is that which consist of better school buildings, more and better teaching facilities.

Bowers and Burkett (2016) found that "improper maintenance of facilities led to lower-than-average Biology students' achievement such as missing of the written word whether on a handout or at the chalkboard". He maintained that inappropriate illumination level abuses the human eye and have unfortunate physiological consequence. He also noted the ill effect of education facilities on biology students' academic achievement is neuron doctrine functions, hyperactivity health and on task behaviour. School facilities mean the acquisition, planning, construction or financing of these school facilities, including classroom, multipurpose, administration and auxiliary space at each school, central support and administrative facilities, interim using, transportation and special education facilities,

together with furniture, equipment and technology, needed to serve directly or indirectly the student population.

School facilities mean only facilities necessary for instructional and related supporting purposes including, but not limited to. Classroom, libraries, media centres, laboratories, cafeterias, physical education spaces, related interior and exterior facilities, and the conduit, wiring and powering of hardware installations for classroom computers or for area network system. Investment in school facilities involves great deals of capital outlay and therefore the proper care of these facilities is an important administrative task, which is the aim of the researcher in assessing the school facilities and academic achievement of students in biology in Calabar South Local Government Area in Cross River State.

Theoretical framework

The theoretical framework for this study was based on Burrhus Frederic Skinner's (1954) Operant Conditioning theory. This theory is considered relevant to the study and will undoubtedly serve as a guide to this study.

Burrhus Frederic Skinner's (1954) Operant Conditioning theory

This theory was developed by B. F. Skinner in 1954. Skinner believed that the goal of psychology should be to find ways to make education enjoyable and effective for all students. His learning theory relied on the assumption that the best way to modify behaviour was to modify the environment. Skinner was a proponent for many instructional strategies that modern-day "progressive" educational reformers advocate for, such as scaffold instructions and immediate feedback. Skinner did not approve of the use of punishment in school or as a behavioural modification technique in general and based his opinions on his own empirical research that found punishment to be ineffective.

Skinner's primary contribution to behavioural management philosophy has been from his research on operant conditioning and reinforcement schedules. An operant is a behaviour that acts on the surrounding environment to produce a consequence. As a result of the consequence, the operant likelihood of reoccurring is affected. The operant is said to be reinforced if the consequence increases the likelihood of the behaviour occurrence. For example, an operant in a typical classroom is learning. A teacher may seek to reinforce this behaviour by offering a reward to reinforce students (e.g food). These findings suggest that teachers using reinforcement in their classroom should be cautious of seeking to reward students every time they perform a behaviour as many teachers using rewards have noted that students are less likely to perform desired behaviour when the rewards are not present, again, effective school facilities will motivate students to learn.

Statement of the problem

Inadequate facilities in the secondary schools are a big problem of the educationists, the parents, the government and even the society as a whole. Inadequate facilities will surely affect the smooth teaching and learning of Biology in all schools. There are some problems outlined below encountered in schools due to lack of adequate facilities. It is known that the academic the first noted, peculiar problem would be generated when there is no inclusive teaching and learning conducted. The conduciveness could be as a result of non-availability of facilities like table and chair in the classroom. There can never be a way of concentration by students. Students cannot be expected to achieve any of the objectives at the end of the lesson. If students have to share chairs with their mates, they would be easily distracted among themselves and the class which is supposed to be actively involved in the learning process turns out to be appealing and there is enough discomfort for the day to discourage the interest of the student for the whole day's work.

Since the interest of the students are very low, they are going to also have a low level of understanding, knowledge to be imparted to the students would not be fully understood. There may also be limitation in understanding. Laboratories are lacking in many schools and in some schools where they can be found reagents and equipment are lacking. For instance, in science class who always learn in abstract that is without practical knowledge of what teacher is saying cannot have effective learning

and this will automatically affect his/her academic achievement. These lacks of laboratories have results to low interest in science subjects today, especially biology.

Also, the non-availability of teaching facilities like computer, textbooks, buildings, charts, chalkboards etc. have hindered the biology students' academic academically and this has resulted in their various level in secondary schools. Finally, it is observed that the biology students supply their acquired knowledge ineffectively since they have not been taught with the practical aspect of their field of specialization if they had the opportunity to make use of facilities in different aspect they would have been effective.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of this research study is to determine the impact of school facilities on academic achievement of students in biology in Calabar South Local Government Area. The specific objectives of the study are as follows:

- i. To determine the influence of school library facilities on students' academic achievement in biology in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State.
- ii. To ascertain the influence of school laboratory on students' academic achievement in biology in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Research question

These research question will be raised for the study:

- i. How do school library facilities relate with the achievement of students in secondary schools in Calabar South Local Government Area?
- ii. How does school laboratory contribute to academic achievement of students in secondary schools in Calabar South Local Government Area?

Statement of hypotheses

The following research questions were raised to guide the study;

- i. There is no significant relationship between school library facilities and academic achievement of students in secondary schools in Calabar South Local Government Area.
- ii. There is no significant relationship between the school laboratory and the academic achievement of students in secondary school in biology in Calabar South Local Government Area.

Significance of the study

The study may be beneficial to the government, stakeholders in education, policy makers, administrators, teachers, counsellors, parents and the general public.

To the government: The government would benefit from this work by discovering the need to making provision for adequate facilities and equipment to the schools.

To researcher: The study may assist the researcher through this research work to understand what lapses exist and make further research that will close the gaps.

To teacher: The study may assist in running their school via the uses of available school facilities efficiently.

To students: The study may assist the students in understanding the concept of learning and motivate them to utilize the school laboratory equipment and other facilities.

Scope of the study

The study is delimited to school facilities and the academic achievement of secondary schools students' academic achievement in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State. The study was defined to the following variables. School library, classrooms, school laboratory and academic achievement of students in secondary schools in Calabar South Local Government Area.

Limitations of the study

Due to the limitations faced by the researcher financially and in terms of time allocated for this work the study would be restricted to secondary schools in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State.

Definition of terms

Academic achievement: The outcome of education, the extent to which students, institution has achieved their educational goal.

Classroom: Physical structure within a school setting where learners can sit to receive their lesson.

Library: Is a building or room in which collection of books, tapes, newspapers etc are kept for people to read study or borrow

School laboratory: This is the school facility where practical activities take place in school, such as physics lab, biology lab, and chemistry lab. Etc.

Research methodology

This chapter presents the procedure adopted in carrying out this study. The chapter is presented under the following sub-headings:

Research design, research area, sampling technique, population of the study, the sample, instrumentation, procedure for data collection, method of data analysis.

Research design

The research design adopted for this study was the survey design. Hence, the survey design was used for opinion and attitude studies, it depends more on questionnaires and interview as means for the collection of relevant data. Survey design was considered appropriate for this study because it allows the researcher to make inferences about the population by selecting and studying only a sample of the population in order to make generalizations about the population in view. Isangedighi, Joshua, Asim and Ekuri (2004) referred to research survey design as a plan, structure and strategy of investigation conceived so as to obtain answers to research questions, and control variances.

Research area

The study was carried out in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State. There are a total of sixteen (16) secondary schools in in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State. The inhabitants of the zone are mainly traders and farmers; in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State is bounded in the north by Calabar municipality in the east by Oron (Akwa Ibom), in the West by Akpabuyo Local Government Area and South by Akamkpa Local Government Area. In terms of land mark, Calabar South headquarters are in the town of Anantigha in te east of the area on the Cross River State. It has a population of 162,383 at the 2006 census. The people of Calabar South Local Government Area are majorly farmers. In the educational sector, Calabar south has various secondary and primary schools as well as Calabar South Local Government Area. The people of Calabar South are predominantly Christians while only two percent are traditional worshippers.

Population of the study

The population for this study was 700 students, comprising all biology students in SS 2 class in Calabar South Local Government Area.

Sampling techniques

The sampling techniques adopted for this study was the simple random sampling technique. This is a means by which a researcher gives every member of his or her population equal and independent opportunity of being selected or represented. A sample is a representative portion of the population which is selected for study because the population too large to examine in its entirety.

The sample

A total of weight eight (88) respondents from 8 secondary schools comprise all biology students in SS2 class were purposively and randomly selected for the study. It consists of both females and the male counterpart.

Instrumentation

The instrument adopted for this study was structured questionnaire and achievement test. Questionnaire was titled “school facilities and students’ academic achievement in biology questionnaire” (SFS AABQ) while the achievement test consists of twenty questions on biology subject. It was designed by the researcher and validated by the supervisor. The questionnaire had two parts, part one was concerned

with demographic information of the respondents such as age, sex and class of the respondents. While part two contained context questions. The options were structured in a four-point Likert scale of strongly agree (SA), agree (A), disagree (D) and strongly disagree (SD).

Validity of the instrument

Validity refers to the degree to which an instrument measure what it is intended to measure. Two kinds of validity were established for the instrument of the study, the face and content validity. Content validity refers to the extent to which the instrument represents the content of the interest of how well the items on the instrument represent or sample the content to be measured. While face validity refers to the way the questionnaire items appear to face value. The instrument was validated by the supervisor as well as experts in measurement and evaluation in the faculty of Education (UNICROSS) and approved its content and validity. Therefore, it was passed to be used for generating data for the study.

Administration of the instrument

The questionnaire and achievement test was the main instrument used for data collection; they were administrated in each of the sampled schools by the researcher. Permission was first gotten from the authorities of each sampled school, who then instructed one teacher to assist the researcher in her mission. The teacher then helped in encouraging other teachers to be addressed by the researcher.

Scoring of the instrument

The method of data analysis depends on each hypothesis. Each hypothesis of the study was restated and variables in it were identified and appropriate statistical analysis techniques for testing them were stated. All the hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance.

Procedure for data analysis

Hypothesis one

There is no significant influence on school facilitates and academic achievement of students in biology.

Independent variable: School facilities

Dependent variable: Students academic achievement in biology

Statistical tool: Independent t-test

Data analysis and interpretation

This chapter presents the results of data analyses carried out on the data gathered for the study. The findings that emerged from these analyses and discussions are also presented. The results are presented according to each hypothesis formulated for the study.

Hypothesis-by-hypothesis presentation of results

In this section, each null hypothesis is restated, and the results of data analyses are also presented. The independent t-test statistical analysis was used for testing the hypotheses.

Hypothesis one

There is no significant relationship between school library and academic achievement of students in secondary schools in Calabar South Local Government Area.

To test this hypothesis, the independent t-test statistical analysis was used. The result is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Independent t-test analysis of the influence on school library facilities and academic achievement of students in secondary schools in Calabar South Local Government Area

Variables	N	\bar{x}	SD	t-cal	t-crit
School library facilities	100	4.43	2.03	2.56	1.96
Academic achievement of students in biology	100	5.32	2.98		

*not significant at $p < .05$, $df = 98$, $crit-t = 1.96$

Result from table 1 above shows that the calculated t-value of 2.56 is greater than the critical or table t-value of 1.96 at .05 alpha level and 98 degrees of freedom. Following this result, the null hypothesis was rejected meaning that there is a significant influence on school library facilities and academic achievement in Biology in secondary schools in Calabar South Local Government Area.

Conclusion and recommendations

Conclusion

Based on the major findings of the study, the researcher concluded that for a teacher to perceive students as per their academic achievement, some qualities such as school library, school laboratory and students' academic achievement in biology in Calabar South Local Government Area must facilitate to ensure effective communication among them and to this end, improve academic effectiveness. Secondly, teachers and school administrators must make provision for quality assurance channel to enhance effectiveness in teaching and learning process and also promote their teacher effectiveness in schools.

Recommendations

The study recommended that certain measures that could be used by teaching staff and other top personnel in fostering quality assurance among teachers in schools.

1. Government should ensure that qualified teaching staff is available in order to promote their teaching effectiveness.
2. School principal should assist make provision for adequate school facilities as well as equipment.
3. Schools should intensify their effort to supervise students' activities while teaching and learning takes place to enhance their communication flow and academic achievement.

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